

Pulsed-Neutron Die-Away Experiments of Propylene Glycol and Mobilmet 423 for Neutron Thermal Scattering Laws Validation

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ABSTRACT

Pulsed-Neutron Die-Away (PNDA) experiments provide a robust technique for investigating neutron moderation and validating thermal scattering laws (TSLs) in hydrogen-rich media. This work presents new PNDA measurements for two such materials: Mobilmet 423 and propylene glycol. Both are liquid hydrocarbons with differing molecular structures and densities, making them suitable candidates for studying how variations in molecular composition and physical properties affect neutron thermalization. Experiments were conducted at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory using a D-T neutron generator, borated polyethylene shielding, and He-3 proportional counters to measure the time-dependent decay of thermalized neutrons following a short neutron pulse. The characteristic decay constants were extracted from the resulting die-away curves and compared with Monte Carlo transport simulations using modern nuclear data libraries. For Mobilmet 423, simulations using the latest heavy paraffinic oil TSL from ENDF/B-VIII.1 showed good agreement with experimental results. In contrast, for propylene glycol, the use of water TSL as a surrogate in simulations led to significant bias, indicating the need for material-specific TSL development. The results highlight the sensitivity of PNDA experiments to TSLs, especially for smaller target geometries. Ongoing work aims to improve experimental characterization including target properties and temperature measurements to further enhance the accuracy and benchmarking value of these experiments.

Keywords: Pulsed-Neutron Die-Away, Thermal Scattering Law, Hydrogenous Liquids, Monte Carlo Simulation, Benchmarking

1. INTRODUCTION

Pulsed-Neutron Die-Away (PNDA) experiments provide a powerful integral technique to investigate neutron moderation and validate thermal scattering laws (TSLs). A short, monoenergetic burst of fast neutrons is introduced into a moderating target, and the subsequent time-dependent decay of the thermalized neutron population is measured. The characteristic decay constant, α , extracted from the die-away curve, serves as the experiment's integral parameter. For properly designed systems, α is strongly dependent on the moderator's thermal scattering behavior, making PNDA experiments a cost effective and sensitive means to validate TSLs used in Monte Carlo transport codes [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Criticality benchmarks have historically served as the primary tool for nuclear data validation, but their usefulness for TSL studies is limited. Biases in critical systems are typically dominated by fissile isotopes, while complex material mixtures and multiple reaction channels obscure the contribution of any single data set. Moreover, critical experiments require licensed facilities and fissile materials, making them costly and less adaptable. In contrast, PNDA benchmarks involve simple, non-fissile targets whose response depends almost exclusively on absorption and scattering cross sections. Their

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geometric simplicity minimizes modeling uncertainty, while their tunable dimensions allow the sensitivity to specific nuclear data to be systematically varied [3, 4]. In addition, varying temperatures for small targets in PNDA benchmarks is significantly easier to implement and control than in criticality benchmarks involving fissile material.

Recent PNDA campaigns at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) have demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach using hydrogenous moderators such as light water, high-density polyethylene (HDPE), and Lucite [1, 2, 3, 4]. These studies confirmed that smaller targets—corresponding to higher geometric buckling—exhibit greater sensitivity to the underlying TSL data. The present work extends these efforts to two liquid hydrocarbon systems, Mobilmet 423 and propylene glycol. Using PNDA as an integral experiment to validate hydrogen-rich liquids, such as Mobilmet 423, is valuable because designing critical experiments with flammable oils can be challenging. Propylene glycol, when used as a coolant in fuel fabrication facilities, can be a significant source of neutron moderation. Mobilmet being a high paraffinic oil is also used as a machining fluid in some fuel processing facilities. By leveraging PNDA as a nuclear validation tool, especially for TSLs, facilities can establish more accurate criticality safety limits and enable greater operational flexibility, avoiding unnecessary process restrictions when accounting for propylene glycol and Mobilmet in their criticality safety evaluations.

This paper describes the theory of the PNDA technique, the experimental setup, results, and simulations performed for both moderators. The measured decay constants are compared with transport simulations using modern nuclear data libraries to assess how well the experimental and calculated integral parameters agree. The comparison also provides a measure of the experiments' sensitivity to uncertainties in thermal scattering and absorption data making them excellent benchmark candidates for hydrogenous liquids.

2. THEORY

The PNDA experiment can be described by one-speed time-dependent diffusion theory for thermal neutrons. Neglecting external sources after the generator pulse, the thermal neutron flux $\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ in a homogeneous, non-multiplying medium satisfies

$$\overline{vD}\nabla^2\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) - \overline{v\Sigma_a}\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t}, \quad (1)$$

where v is the neutron speed, D is the diffusion coefficient, and Σ_a is the macroscopic absorption cross section. Both \overline{vD} and $\overline{v\Sigma_a}$ terms are spectrally averaged over the asymptotic neutron energy distribution. By separation of variables, the spatial and temporal dependence can be expressed as a sum of exponentially decaying modes. After a sufficient time following the pulse, higher-order modes vanish and only the fundamental mode remains:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \phi_0(\mathbf{r})e^{-\alpha t} + R(t), \quad (2)$$

where α [s^{-1}] is the fundamental decay constant of the system and $R(t)$ accounts for residual background or room-return effects. In practice, α is obtained by fitting the measured neutron counts versus time after the pulse to Eq. (2).

The decay constant can be related to material and geometric properties through the diffusion expansion:

$$\alpha_0 = \overline{v\Sigma_a} + D_0B_0^2 - CB_0^4 + \dots \quad (3)$$

where B_0^2 is the geometric buckling determined by the moderator's dimensions and boundary conditions. For a finite cylinder of radius R and height H ,

$$B_0^2 = \left(\frac{2.405}{R + \delta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\pi}{H + \delta}\right)^2, \quad (4)$$

with $\delta \approx 0.71\lambda_{tr}$ denoting the extrapolation distance and λ_{tr} the transport mean free path. The diffusion coefficient itself depends on the transport cross section Σ_{tr} as $D = 1/[3\Sigma_{tr}]$. Both Σ_{tr} and Σ_a are functions of the microscopic cross sections and atomic densities of the constituent elements.

Here, D_0 [$\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is the asymptotic diffusion coefficient in an infinite medium, and C [$\text{cm}^4\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$] is the *cooling coefficient*. The cooling coefficient represents a geometric correction: higher-energy neutrons leak preferentially at the system boundaries, so the surviving neutron population cools to an average energy lower than thermal equilibrium. For large, weakly leaking moderators the CB_0^4 term becomes negligible and Equation (3) can be reduced to a first-order approximation. On the other hand, for targets with large geometric buckling—corresponding to smaller physical dimensions and stronger neutron leakage—the higher-order term becomes more significant and decreases the predicted α_0 relative to the first-order diffusion prediction.

Equation (3) shows that the die-away constant α depends on both absorption and scattering properties. As the sample size decreases, B_0^2 increases and the scattering-dependent term dominates, making α more sensitive to the diffusion coefficient and thus to the thermal scattering laws in the medium. Conversely, for larger samples with small B_0^2 , absorption effects dominate and α becomes less sensitive to scattering.

3. EXPERIMENT

The PNDA measurements were performed using a D-T neutron generator, a borated polyethylene shielding box, four ^3He proportional counters, and dedicated signal-processing electronics. Figure 1 on the left (a) shows the experimental setup of the box and generator in the low scatter facility at LLNL and on the right (b) is the setup inside the shielding box for one of the targets. The shielding assembly, fabricated from 2.45-cm-thick 5%-borated high-density polyethylene (ShieldwexTM 201HD) lined with 0.32-cm-thick cadmium sheet, served to reduce neutron room return and reflections from surrounding equipment. The neutron generator was positioned directly beneath the enclosure, and the 14-MeV neutrons entered the target cavity through a small beam port in the base of the box. This configuration provided a well-defined irradiation geometry while maintaining a low background.

(a) Experimental setup outside of the PNDA box.

(b) Experimental PNDA target within the box.

Figure 1. PNDA experimental setup in the low scatter facility at LLNL.

Neutron pulses were produced by a Thermo Scientific P-383 D-T generator operated at maximum settings of 130 kV and 60 μA , yielding an emission rate on the order of 3×10^8 n/s. Each pulse had a constant pulse width of 100 μs across targets, with pulse repetition frequencies of either 400 Hz for the the largest target or 570 kHz for the smaller targets. The generator's transistor-transistor logic (TTL)

trigger output provided the time reference for data acquisition.

Detection of moderated neutrons was done with four cylindrical ^3He proportional counters (Reuter-Stokes), each 10.18 cm in active length and 1.17 cm in diameter, filled with 4 atm of ^3He gas. The detectors were mounted inside the shielding enclosure around the target cavity to monitor the leakage flux associated with the fundamental mode. Signals from each detector were fed through Precision Data Technology PDT20A modules, which combine a high-voltage supply, pre-amplifier, shaping amplifier, and discriminator in a single unit. The PDT20A modules operated from a 12-V supply. The operating voltage was set to 1655 V for each PDT20A and proportional counter pair.

The pulses were recorded in list-mode using a PTR-32 time-tagging module. The PTR-32 provides 100-ns timestamp resolution and accepts multiple input channels, allowing all detector outputs and the generator trigger signal to be logged simultaneously.

Data from the PTR-32 were post-processed to reconstruct die-away curves referenced to the start of each neutron pulse. For each target, time-tagged events from hundreds of thousands of pulses were accumulated into 1- μs bins to obtain a smooth neutron count-versus-time distribution. The exponential region of this curve was identified and fitted to Eq. (2) using a non-linear least-squares procedure to determine the characteristic decay constant α . The same methodology was applied to both experimental and simulated datasets to maintain consistency in the determination of the integral parameter.

4. RESULTS

Simulations of the experiments were done in MCNP6.3.0[®]. Figure 2 shows the geometry in the models. Each model consists of a 14.1 MeV isotropic disk source to irradiate the cylindrical targets placed inside the shielding box. The simplified simulations simulate 10^9 neutrons in a single pulse and replicate the 100- μs pulse width of the experiments. The final benchmark will tally the neutron flux in all four detectors and apply the ^3He absorption reaction cross section. A time bin structure of 1- μs was used in the models to match the bin size of the post-processed experiment data. The simulations were run with ENDF/B-VIII.0 data processed with the LANL NJOY code and stored in ACE files [6]. The simulations assumed that the temperature of every sample was 294K.

Figure 2. Illustration of the PNDA experimental design in the models.

Determining the integral parameter α_0 for each target requires specifying the time interval needed for the fit. The presence of the high-order spatial modes of the flux can overestimate α_0 if the fit region is chosen too early. On the other hand, α_0 can be underestimated or contaminated by room return if the fit region is chosen too late on the curve. To avoid this, the fit method relies on a visual plateau in many

fits along the decay curve. Figure 3 shows an example of an α -values fit curve overlaying a typical experimental decay curve. Here, a time interval of $50 \mu\text{s}$ is used at the start of the decay region of the curve to apply the first fit, then the interval is slid to the next $50 \mu\text{s}$ and the fit is applied again. Once all the following $50 \mu\text{s}$ intervals along the curve are fitted, a plateau region can be seen where α_0 is selected at 0.17 ms. The selection of the time interval requires an iterative process at the start of the analysis to generate the α -values fit curve with the optimal plateau region. The uncertainty in α_0 is obtained as a result of the weighted fit algorithm by minimizing χ^2 between the measured/modeled curve and the fitted function in Eq. (2). More details on the determination of the uncertainty can be found in the PNDA benchmarks for HDPE, Lucite, and H_2O materials released in the ICSBEP handbook [1, 2]. The same process is applied for both the simulated and experimental decay curves.

Figure 3. Experimental decay curve (black) and fitted α values (blue). The dashed line indicates the point in time where α_0 is determined.

4.1. Propylene Glycol

Propylene glycol ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$) is a coolant used in some fuel processing facilities due to its stable thermal property. Its close proximity to the fissile material means it must be considered when performing nuclear criticality evaluations that rely on accurate representation of neutron interactions in the models. Figure 4 shows the decay curves obtained from the propylene glycol experiments on the right and from the MCNP6.3 models on the left. Each curve is labeled by the target's buckling. The decay constants for each of the experimental and simulated curves is determined using the methodology described in Section 4 where a distribution of α values is constructed and a plateau region is used to obtain α_0 . Table I shows the radii and heights of the propylene glycol targets, the evaluated buckling, the fitted decay constants from the experiment and simulations, and the calculated bias. The uncertainty in both experimental and modeled decay constants is determined using the same methodology described in Section 4. Both experimental and simulated results demonstrate the decay constants increase with buckling indicating faster leakage of the thermal neutron population for smaller targets. Here, the simulations were done with ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library. Due to the lack of propylene glycol TSL, the water TSL was used in the models as the closest surrogate evaluation. Although propylene glycol contains both C-H and O-H bonds, the vibrational modes stemming from O-H groups influence TSL more significantly than C-H groups [7], making the water TSL a more appropriate proxy compared to hydrocarbon-based TSLs where only C-H bonds are present. The bias results show a consistently higher simulated α than experimental α with a maximum of 20% for the smallest target. Although the water TSL offers a close

chemical approximation, it is likely the hydrogen dynamics of propylene glycol are not adequately represented by water. In order to make a definitive assessment on these results, more characterization is needed in the final benchmark. This includes precise measurements of the material composition, dimensions, and density. The final benchmark models will also rely on measured temperature values as opposed to the 293.6 K assumed temperature.

Figure 4. Experimental and simulated (MCNP6.3) decay curves for the propylene glycol targets using ENDF/B-VIII.0 data.

Table I. propylene glycol target parameters, experiment decay constants, and simulated decay constants with MCNP6.3 and ENDF/B-VIII.0.

Radius (cm)	Height (cm)	Buckling (cm^{-2})	Experiment α (ms^{-1})	Model α (ms^{-1})	$\frac{C-E}{E}\%$
5.935	4.100	0.867	21.448 ± 0.205	26.087 ± 0.032	21.62 ± 1.17
5.935	5.319	0.629	17.615 ± 0.112	19.945 ± 0.008	13.23 ± 0.72
5.935	9.942	0.380	12.225 ± 0.088	13.327 ± 0.004	9.01 ± 0.79
8.654	13.916	0.183	8.585 ± 0.065	9.146 ± 0.001	6.54 ± 0.81

4.2. Mobilmet 423

Mobilmet is a paraffinic oil used in some fuel processing facilities as a machining fluid due to its high lubricity characteristic. Similar to propylene glycol, its close proximity to the fissile material and its ability to moderate neutrons, requires that its accounted for when establishing model-derived facility safety requirements. Figure 5 shows the decay curves obtained from the Mobilmet 423 experiments on the right and from the MCNP6.3 models on the left. Table II shows the radii and heights of the Mobilmet 423 targets, the evaluated buckling, the fitted decay constants from the experiment and simulations, and the calculated bias. The height of the target was derived from mass measurements of the container with and without the oil, inner radius measurement of the container, and the density. While the simulations were done with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library, a newly evaluated heavy paraffinic oil TSL [8], included in ENDF/B-VIII.1 [9], was used to provide the Mobilmet TSL in the models. The bias results show better agreement between the models and experiments across targets compared to propylene glycol. The trend of the bias results and their uncertainties shows overlap for row 1, 2, 3 and again for row 1 and row 4. More experimental characterization of the targets will need to be done to confidently draw conclusion of this trend.

Figure 5. Experimental and simulated (MCNP6.3) decay curves for the Mobilmet targets using ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 for heavy paraffinic oil TSL.

Table II. Mobilmet 423 target parameters, experiment decay constants, and simulated decay constants with MCNP6.3

Radius (cm)	Height (cm)	Buckling (cm^{-2})	Experiment α (ms^{-1})	Model α (ms^{-1})	$\frac{C-E}{E}$ %
5.935	4.754	0.717	18.682 ± 0.159	18.976 ± 0.012	1.57 ± 0.86
5.935	6.473	0.516	14.935 ± 0.114	15.048 ± 0.007	0.76 ± 0.77
5.935	11.788	0.351	11.349 ± 0.049	11.46 ± 0.002	0.98 ± 0.44
8.654	16.914	0.166	8.367 ± 0.073	8.594 ± 0.001	2.71 ± 0.90

5. CONCLUSIONS

New PNDA experiments with propylene glycol and Mobilmet targets are presented. Simulations of these experiments were done in MCNP6.3 as means to provide TSL data validation. For both materials, results showed trends that correlated the decay constant's sensitivity to TSLs. The large bias results in the propylene glycol targets point to the need of a new TSL evaluation for this material. The simulations with the Mobilmet targets were done using the TSL evaluation in ENDF/B-VIII.1 for heavy paraffinic oil and exhibited good agreement with experiment.

Future work will require accurate characterizations of the targets' composition, geometry, and density. Any modeling errors in these parameters can lead to additional biases originating from the models. Additional details such as the experimental temperature will also be included in order to create high-quality benchmark and better understand the source of bias.

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